

ASSESSMENT OF TV IMAGE QUALITY IN THE ABSENCE OF HF COEFFICIENTS IN LIFTING WAVELET FILTERS

Akhmedova A.

Tashkent University of Information Technologies (TUIT), Tashkent, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14190052>

***Аннотация.** Данная работа посвящена проблеме повышения эффективности видеокодирования в системах цифрового вещательного и прикладного телевидения на основе минимизации видеоданных. Поэтому оценивается влияние обнуления высокочастотных коэффициентов лифтинговых вейвлет фильтров LeGall (5,3), Deslauriers-Debuc (9,7) и Deslauriers-Debuc (13,7) на качество декодированных ТВ изображений. Приводятся результаты экспериментальных исследований показывающие, как меняется качество тестовых изображений различных сюжетов и жанров вследствие обнуления различных массивов ВЧ вейвлет коэффициентов и их комбинаций.*

***Ключевые слова:** цифровое телевидение, ТВ изображения, видеокодирование, вейвлет преобразования, вейвлет фильтры, вейвлет коэффициенты, качество изображений.*

***Abstract.** The problem of increasing the efficiency of video coding in digital broadcasting and applied television systems based on minimization of video data are considered in this paper. Therefore, the effect of zeroing the high-frequency coefficients of the lifting wavelet filters LeGall (5.3), Deslauriers-Debuc (9.7) and Deslauriers-Debuc (13.7) on the quality of decoded TV images is estimated. The results of experimental studies showing how the quality of test images of various plots and genres changes due to zeroing various arrays of high-frequency wavelet coefficients and their combinations are presented.*

***Keywords:** digital television, TV images, video coding, wavelet transforms, wavelet filters, wavelet coefficients, image quality.*

Introduction

Nowadays television has become an integral part of our society, since it allows us to convey information to viewers from almost anywhere in the world. Moreover, in addition to broadcast television, applied television systems are also actively developing, allowing for visual monitoring of processes in various areas of human activity. These include maintaining public order, traffic flow, various processes in hard-to-reach or dangerous technological zones, medicine, exploration of the earth from space, satellites and planets of the solar system, deep space and etc. At the same time, the requirements for the quality of television images are also constantly growing, for which high and ultra-high-definition video systems are being introduced, generating huge digital video data streams that must be transmitted in real time. And storing such volumes of video data is quite problematic, since if in standard definition television (SD) with a resolution of 720×576 an hourly transmission has a volume of approximately 110 GB, then in ultra-high-definition television 4K with a resolution of 3840×2160 the volume of an hourly transmission will already contain 2.24 TB. Therefore, to reduce the volume of video data, special video codecs are used, based on the elimination of various types of redundant (predictable) information contained in television images.

At present the most widely used codecs in broadcast and applied television are MPEG -4-10 AVC, H.264 and its improved modification H.265. These codecs can provide good image

quality, on average, at digital flow rates (bit rates) of 1-2.5 Mbit/s, depending on the codec type used. But the problem with video compression is that the amount of redundant information in frames is determined by the type of video plot. Thus, images with large, relatively homogeneous objects contain a lot of redundant information and therefore are well compressed, while fine-grained images contain little predictable information and, therefore, are poorly compressed. Thus, in the lossless encoding mode, the size of “the aircraft” test frame is compressed by 25 times (Fig. 1), and “the girl” test data are compressed only by 5 times (Fig. 2), that is, 5 times worse, and leads to different sizes of such frames.

Fig. 1. The result of “the aircraft” image coding in the lossless compression mode shows a compression of 25 times, which is 48.127 kB

Accordingly, when transmitting images over communication channels with a constant bandwidth, different frame sizes in a video sequence can lead to poorly compressed frames falling out of the video stream, causing jerky movements on the screen. So, to stabilize the bit rate during encoding, poorly compressed frames are compressed extra by the codec quantizer by removing some of the useful information [1]. And this leads to the occurrence of block and other types of distortions in decoded images. Fig. 3 shows the appearance of “the girl” image, when its data volume is compressed by 50 times.

Fig. 2. The result of “the girl” image coding in the lossless compression mode shows a compression of 5 times, which is 245 KB

Fig. 3. Visual quality of “the girl” image after 50 times compression

As could be seen from the given figure, visually the quality of the image became very badly spoiled by block distortions and had low clarity. That is why the special low-pass

deblocking filters smooth out brightness differences at block boundaries in the H.264 and H.265 video codecs. However, due to the use of deblocking filters in such codecs at low encoding bitrates, fine-grained images may have a blurred appearance and reduced clarity, as shown in Fig. 4. Therefore, to preserve the visual quality of digital images, especially in high-definition and ultra-high-definition television systems (4K and 8K), more efficient video compression ways are needed.

Fig. 4. Visual quality of the original image captured with a bit rate of 29 Mbps (a) and encoded one with the H.264 codec with a bit rate of 1 Mbps (b)

The statement of the problem

Since the amount of redundant information in television images is determined by the structure of the video plot, more effective methods for reducing the volume of video data must be developed to preserve the visual quality of fine-grained images.

One of such methods of reducing the original volume of video information in a frame can be the use of discrete wavelet transforms, used in the JPEG-2000 standard and some experimental video codecs [2]. However, the wavelet transforms (WT) themselves do not change the pixel amount of the frame, but only redistribute it between the arrays of LF (Low-Frequency) and HF (High-Frequency) coefficients, as shown in Fig. 5 [1].

Fig. 5. The principle of redistribution of image pixels into arrays of low-frequency and high-frequency coefficients

In the most common lifting scheme of WT, the array of LF coefficients contains the most informative part of the image, which are 2-fold size reduced; and the array of HF coefficients

contains errors of predicting pixel values. But the total number of coefficients in the LF and HF arrays is equal to the number of pixels in the original image [3].

Since the images are a two-dimensional pixel array, the WT process is performed in 2 stages: first, in the horizontal direction row by row, and then in the vertical direction or vice versa. In this case, odd elements usually correspond to the LF coefficients, and even ones to the HF coefficients. After the LF and HF coefficients are formed, the arrays are separated to combine the LF and HF coefficients into the corresponding arrays. In this case, the differences between the true and predicted pixel values (prediction errors) are written into the even positions of the coefficient array, and the sums of the values of neighboring pixels with averaged prediction error values are written into the odd positions. As a result of the two-dimensional (horizontal and vertical) WT, a structure of 4 segments is formed, shown in Fig. 6, where LL is an array of LF coefficients, HH is an array of HF coefficients, and the HL and LH arrays form their combinations. Accordingly, if all arrays except LL are zeroed, the frame size will be reduced by 4, which significantly increases the efficiency of video coding [4, 5]. However, it is interesting to determine how zeroing of one or more arrays with high-frequency coefficients affects the level of introduced distortions and, accordingly, the quality of decoded images.

Fig. 6. The structure of the grouping of the VP coefficients after direct two-dimensional transformation of the original image.

Experimental Research

For the experimental evaluation of the effect of zeroing the high-frequency wavelet coefficients, two types of lifting wavelet filters used in the Dirac video codec were selected: a short filter on **LeGall wavelets (5,3)** and a long one on **Deslauriers-Debuc wavelets (13,7)** [6]. The generalized algorithm of direct transformation is described by the following expressions [6]:

LeGall (5,3):

$$D_{2i+1} = b_{2i+1} - (b_{2i} + b_{2i+2} + 1)/2 - \text{HF filter}$$

$$S_{2i} = b_{2i} + (d_{2i-1} + d_{2i+1} + 2)/4 - \text{LF filter}$$

Deslauriers-Debuc (13,7):

$$D_{2i+1} = b_{2i+1} - (((b_{2i} + b_{2i+2}) \times 9 + (b_{2i-2} + b_{2i+4}) \times (-1)) + 8)/16$$

$$S_{2i} = d_{2i} + ((d_{2i-1} + d_{2i+1}) \times 9 + (d_{i-3} + d_{i+3}) \times (-1) + 16)/32.$$

Where D and S are the corresponding arrays of high-frequency and low-frequency coefficients, and b are the pixel values of the image.

Three images with low, high and medium detail were selected for the experiments They are presented in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. A set of test images with low, medium and high detail.

The special codec software was created to conduct the experiments. It was written by the C++ programming language in the Borland Builder-6 environment, having a convenient control interface. Accordingly, when conducting experimental studies, each test image was first subjected to direct wavelet transformation by the specified wavelet filters, then one type (HL or LH or HH) of high-frequency coefficients was zeroed. After that the inverse WT was performed to analyze the quality of the decoded images. The effect of zeroing several types of high-frequency coefficients on the image quality was also analyzed.

To evaluate the quality of decoded images, both the visual impression and the MSE (*Mean Squared Error – root mean square error*) were applied. MSE estimates the deviations of the pixel values of the original and decoded images, using the following formula [7]:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} |L(i, j) - K(i, j)|^2, \quad (1)$$

where m and n are the horizontal and vertical dimensions of the image. L(i, j) is the value of the pixel of the original image, and K(i, j) is the value of the pixel of the decoded image with the same coordinates (i, j).

If the images match, the MSE value is 0. Accordingly, the metric value increases with increasing distortions inside the image. This metric does not correspond to our visual sensations, but it allows us to quantitatively evaluate the distortions introduced by different coding algorithms, so it has become widespread.

The results of experimental studies on the assessment of the influence of zeroing the HF WT coefficients on the quality of test television images are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Tab.1.

Values of distortions introduced into reconstructed images when zeroing arrays of high-frequency coefficients of the WT on LeGal (5.3) wavelets

Type of image	Distortions according to the MSE metric, %							
	Zeroable WT coefficient segments							
	Without zeroing	HL	HH	LH	HL HH	HL LH	LH HH	FUL
Airplane	0	5.9	2,2	5.9	2,2	2,2	5, 9	5.9
Young woman	0	8.4	6.8	7.4	6.9	7.7	7.7	9
Nature	0	9.5	8.3	10.4	10	11.3	11.6	12

Tab. 2.

Values of distortions introduced into reconstructed images when zeroing arrays of high-frequency coefficients of the WT on Deslauriers - Debut (13.7) wavelets

Type of image	Distortions according to the MSE metric, %							
	Zeroable WT coefficient segments							
	Without zeroing	HL	HH	LH	HL HH	HL LH	LH HH	FUL
Airplane	0,1	2.4	1.8	5.4	1.8	5.4	5.4	5.4
Young woman	0 ,1	7.8	6.4	7	6.6	6.8	6.8	8.2
Nature	0	9.5	8.3	10.4	10	10.4	10.4	11.2

As follows from the presented results of experimental studies, the magnitude of distortions associated with the zeroing of various segments of high-frequency wavelet coefficients is influenced by the length of the wavelet filters and the type of image greater, than the zeroed segments themselves. Thus, when processing a relatively homogeneous large-structure image of an Airplane shorter LeGal (5.3) wavelet filters introduce a slightly higher level of distortion (5.9%) than the longer one Deslauriers - Debut (13.7) (5.4%) when all segments of the high-frequency coefficients are zeroed. And when processing a fine-structured image of nature, the level of distortion increases to 12% on the LeGal filter and to 11.2% on the Deslauriers - Debut filter. As for the influence of the types of zeroed segments of the high-frequency coefficients, zeroing the HH and HLHH segments introduces the lowest level of distortion into the reconstructed test images, but this mainly manifests itself only in large-structured images. And in the images of Nature and the Young woman, which have a fine structure, the type of zeroed segments has a fairly low influence on the level of introduced distortions. At the same time, it should be noted that the MSE metric values do not correspond to our visual perception.

Thus, images with high distortion values according to the MSE metric can be perceived as good and vice versa, images of poor visual quality can have low MSE metric values, as shown in Fig. 8. It shows the visual quality of the original and restored images with MSE = 12%.

Nevertheless, this metric is actively used in practice, as it allows quantitative characterization of the work of various encoder and algorithms.

Fig. 8. Comparative quality of the original (a) and reconstructed image (b) with MSE = 12%.

The visual quality of the image with completely zeroed HF coefficients is acceptable. Thus, the use of zeroing HF coefficients of the two-dimensional discrete wavelet transform does not greatly worsen the visual quality of images and allows to reduce the volume of video data by 4 times, can significantly increase the efficiency of video compression in broadcast and applied television systems.

REFERENCES

1. I.A.Gavrilov, T.G.Rakhimov, A.N.Puziy, H.H.Nosirov, Sh.M.Kadirov “Digital television” Tashkent, 2016 г., 380 p.
2. Peter Wilson, Tim Borer, Thomas David. Semeystvo sistem tsifrovogo sjstiya Dirac rasshryaetsya. Journal 625. No.3, 2007 .
3. V.I. Vorobyov, V.G. Gribuni. VUS Theoriya i praktika wavelet preobrazovaniy., 1999. 204 p.
4. D. A. Fedorov. Method of image scaling with an integer coefficient based on the wavelet transform. //Optical Journal, 80, 3, 2013. pp. 52-57.
5. Anora Akhmedova, Igor Gavrilov, Anastasia Puziy, Vladislav Gubtnko, Alkhamov Radik. Efficiency Estimation of Video Compression with a Bidirectional TV Images Resizing. 2024 IEEE 25TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF YOUNG PROFESSIONALS IN ELECTRON DEVICES AND MATERIALS. May 2-3, 2024. Altai Republic. Russia.
6. Dirac developer Support
https://dirac.sourceforge.net/documentation/algorithm/algorithm/wlt_transform.xht
7. Yu. I. Monich, V. V. Starovoytov. Quality assessments for digital image analysis.//Artificial Intelligence No. 4, 2008. pp. 376-386